
EFFECT OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT TASKS ON THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS

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Abstract

This article explores the effective use of formative assessment (FA) tasks in mathematics lessons as a tool for improving student learning. While FA is recognized as a promising method for enhancing teaching and learning, it is essential to study how teachers implement it during lessons to ensure its contribution to students' knowledge quality. This study involved a survey of mathematics teachers, leading to the development of a rubric for presenting FA tasks to students. The impact of FA on educational quality was analyzed through an experimental study. The results demonstrated that timely feedback, facilitated through the effective use of FA tasks, significantly contributed to students' academic success in aggregate assessments.

Key words

Formative assessment (FA), quality of education, mathematical education, academic achievement, FA assignment, updated educational program

1 Introduction

Between 2016 and 2019, as part of the phased implementation of the Updated Educational Curriculum (UEC) in Kazakhstan, FA was introduced to promote constructive learning and align the national education system with global standards. This assessment approach systematically monitors students' academic progress and enhances learning outcomes through timely feedback. However, the effective implementation of FA tasks remains limited. Empirical studies indicate that some educators struggle with designing and administering these tasks in accordance with methodological requirements. In some cases, FA tasks are developed in a formalistic manner, failing to achieve their intended pedagogical objectives.

FA is a process that facilitates students' continuous progress while fostering communication between teachers and students. It is conducted as part of daily classroom activities and serves as an ongoing indicator of students' academic performance. Research highlights that FA is an essential tool that enhances students' motivation, allowing teachers to monitor their progress while considering individual learning needs (Black & Wiliam, 1998). Effective FA relies on clearly defined assessment criteria that should be presented in accessible language, making them comprehensible to both students and parents. This approach enhances objectivity and transparency in assessment, ensuring students understand the criteria by which their work is evaluated.

To better understand how FA contributes to academic achievement, it is essential to analyze the key mechanisms that influence students' engagement and performance (Rakoczy et al., 2019). Research on FA has evolved in two primary directions: early studies focused on

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distinguishing FA from other assessment methods (Yan & Pastore, 2022; Wiliam & Thompson, 2008), whereas more recent research examines the extent to which teachers implement FA in practice and its impact on students' learning outcomes (Yan & Pastore, 2022; Wylie, 2020).

This study explores two key aspects related to the impact of FA on student achievement. First, it defines the essence of FA (see Sections 2.1) and identifies the factors influencing students' perceptions of it (see Sections 2.2). Second, it examines the extent to which FA tasks improve students' academic performance. A diagnostic analysis of survey data collected from mathematics teachers was conducted to assess FA integration in their teaching practices. Additionally, a rubric for presenting FA tasks in mathematics lessons was developed and its effectiveness was analyzed.

2 Background

This study was based on theoretical and empirical conclusions on formative assessment to study the impact of teachers on the quality of students' knowledge, effectively using formative assessment tasks in teaching.

2.1 2.1 Formative assessment

Assessment is not merely a tool for determining learning outcomes; it is a comprehensive process that goes beyond quantifying students' mastery of educational content. It also facilitates an understanding of the underlying reasons for their achievements or difficulties. Research by various scholars highlights that assessment is an essential and central component of the educational system (Black, 1993).

Historically, the primary function of assessment has been to determine students' readiness to progress to the next level of education (Moon, 2005). In contemporary education, assessment is widely used to evaluate what students know and what they can do (Baird, Andrich, Hopfenbeck, & Stobart, 2017). In this sense, assessment serves as a mechanism for measuring learning achievements and fostering educational development.

The concept of formative assessment can be traced back to Scriven (1967), who explored the process of developing new educational programs. However, the modern reform of assessment and the growing recognition of formative assessment were significantly influenced by the publication of Black and Wiliam's seminal work "*Inside the Black Box*" (1998). In this study, the authors reviewed over 250 research papers on classroom assessment and demonstrated its pivotal role in enhancing both teaching and learning.

Formative assessment is an interactive process that makes learning more dynamic and adaptable. It serves as a tool for improving educational quality, enabling teachers to refine their instructional strategies and helping students identify areas for improvement. For assessment to be effective, diagnostic evaluation and instructional adaptation must be conducted in a timely manner.

Since Black and Wiliam (1998) introduced their perspectives on assessment for learning, numerous empirical studies have been conducted across different educational levels and subject areas to evaluate the effectiveness of formative assessment (Black & Wiliam, 2009; Nicol & MacFarlane-Dick, 2006; Sadler, 1989; Topping, 1998; York, 2003). The findings of these studies consistently indicate that formative assessment contributes significantly to enhancing student learning outcomes and improving overall educational quality.

The FA allows teachers to identify the difficulties that students face when mastering a particular topic. This approach ensures timely support for students by the school administration and teachers, where grades are considered not only points, but also more important. Teachers need to explain to students what these grades mean and how they can improve their learning process.

The FA provides continuous feedback between the student and the teacher, without scoring and grading. This creates the opportunity to identify the student's current opportunities, find challenges, motivate, motivate learning and recognition, help achieve the best results, timely correct the learning process, and develop the student's professional skills (Shepard, 2000; Pellegrino, Chudowsky, Glaser, 2001; Heritage, 2010; Wiliam, 2009). First of all, this is achieved through the orientation of the teacher and students throughout the lesson not on quantitative indicators, but on a qualitative analysis of their educational activities.

2.2 Attitude of students to formative assessment

Students' perceptions of FA influence their motivation and learning outcomes. Their attitudes can be either positive or negative, depending on various factors.

Positive Attitudes:

- *Motivation: When students view FA as an opportunity for improvement, they engage actively in learning.*
- *Feedback Efficiency: Accurate and fair feedback enhances students' understanding and ability to correct mistakes.*
- *Self-Evaluation: FA fosters students' ability to reflect on their learning, increasing responsibility.*
- *Personal Support: When individual learning needs are considered, students find FA fair and beneficial.*

Negative Attitudes:

- *Misunderstanding: If students do not understand the purpose of FA, they may perceive it as an unnecessary burden.*
- *Incorrect Feedback: Unclear or unfair feedback demotivates students.*
- *Lack of Reflection Skills: Some students struggle with self-evaluation, leading to frustration.*
- *Pressure: Constant assessment may create anxiety, reducing engagement.*

To achieve a positive effect of formative assessment, it is important to understand the perception and attitude of students towards it (Bader, Burner, Hoem Iversen, & Varga, 2019; Guo & Yan, 2019). It has been shown that students' perception of formative assessment is related to how they use it (Jonsson, 2013; Kyaruzi, Strijbos, Ufer, & Brown, 2019). Usually, if students find feedback helpful, their attitude towards it will be positive. Another important factor that affects students' perception of FA is the time to receive feedback. The comments received after completing the lesson are less interesting and useless (Jonsson, 2013). Feedback is the process of informing and receiving comments about specific actions, situations, issues that lead to the achievement of a goal. It gives an idea of how the educational process is going, informs about the achievements and gaps in the knowledge of each student. Feedback ensures the success of learning if it is carried out in an atmosphere of mutual respect and goodwill and

gives students time to answer correctly and correct mistakes. Feedback should be a clear, understandable, timely and complete topic. FA is a non-stop feedback process.

Some students see formative assessment as an external motivator (Weurlander, Söderberg, Scheja, Hult, & Wernerson, 2012). The formation of motivation occurs constantly in the educational process through the selection of books that correspond to the level of reading competence of students, interesting and different ways and methods of teaching. The internal motivation of the student is longer and more effective. This will allow the student to immerse himself in the proposed material, look for detailed answers and achieve high results. The teacher should strive to form the internal motivation of students in assessment activities. The combination of external and internal motivation is an important condition for achieving a good result.

2.3 Comparison of Formative Assessment and Alternative Assessment Methods

Formative assessment is a key approach used to continuously monitor students' learning progress, provide timely feedback, and improve the learning process. This method helps identify students' knowledge gaps and allows for necessary adjustments to enhance their understanding. However, alternative assessment methods such as *peer assessment*, *self-assessment* and *digital assessment tools* are also widely implemented in education.

The following section presents a comparative analysis of formative assessment and its alternative methods (Table 1,2,3)

Table 1. Formative Assessment vs. Self-Assessment

Comparison Criteria	Formative Assessment	Self-Assessment
Primary Objective	Facilitates structured evaluation and feedback from teachers.	Encourages students to independently assess their own learning progress.
Assessor	Teachers and students work collaboratively in the assessment process.	Students evaluate their own work.
Feedback Type	Detailed feedback from teachers with structured improvement strategies.	Self-reflection without external validation.
Assessment Method	Based on explicit descriptors and structured criteria .	Based on students' personal judgment, which may be subjective.
Student Role	Identifies difficulties, receives teacher feedback, and adjusts learning strategies.	Independently reflects on performance, but objectivity may be lacking.
Advantages	Ensures objectivity and structured guidance for students.	Encourages student autonomy and self-regulation.
Limitations	Requires teacher supervision and significant time investment.	Students may overestimate or underestimate their performance.

Table 2. Formative Assessment vs. Peer Assessment

Comparison Criteria	Formative Assessment	Peer Assessment
Primary Objective	Enhances learning by monitoring students' progress and providing corrective feedback.	Encourages students to evaluate and provide feedback on each other's work.
Assessor	Teachers or a combination of teachers and students.	Students assess their peers' work.
Feedback Type	Teachers provide structured and specific feedback.	Students exchange feedback, but quality and fairness may vary.

Assessment Method	Based on predefined criteria and descriptors for accuracy.	Evaluation depends on students' subjective interpretations.
Student Role	Receives teacher feedback to improve learning.	Provides feedback to peers, but may lack the expertise for effective assessment.
Advantages	Offers structured and objective evaluation.	Encourages collaboration and critical thinking among students.
Limitations	Requires significant time and effort from educators.	Feedback may lack reliability and consistency.

Table 3. Formative Assessment vs. Digital Assessment

Comparison Criteria	Formative Assessment	Digital Assessment
Primary Objective	Continuously monitors and improves students' learning through teacher feedback and self-reflection.	Uses technology to assess students' knowledge and provide automated feedback.
Assessment Timing	Conducted in real-time during lessons and adjusted based on students' responses.	Often instant, providing immediate results after task completion.
Feedback Type	Personalized, qualitative feedback from teachers, tailored to individual student needs.	Automated feedback, mostly quantitative (scores, performance analytics).
Assessment Method	Based on structured rubrics, teacher evaluations, and student self-reflection.	Includes multiple-choice quizzes, AI-generated feedback, and adaptive assessments.
Student Engagement	Actively involves students in self-assessment, peer evaluation, and teacher-guided learning adjustments.	Provides data-driven insights but may not fully engage students in self-reflection.
Objectivity and Reliability	Ensures contextualized and individualized evaluation but may be influenced by teacher subjectivity.	Highly objective in scoring but may lack contextual understanding of student responses.
Adaptability	Can be adjusted based on real-time classroom interactions and student needs.	Uses predefined algorithms but may not accommodate individual learning styles effectively.
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourages deeper learning and reflection. - Provides detailed qualitative feedback. - Adaptable to different learning needs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immediate and scalable. - Reduces teacher workload. - Provides data-driven insights for performance tracking.
Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time-consuming for teachers. - Requires subjective judgment, which may vary. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lacks personalized insights. - Limited ability to assess critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

2.4 Research question

This study examines whether a rubric for presenting FA tasks in mathematics lessons improves students' academic performance.

2.4.1 Research work the following research questions were considered

Does the use of a rubric for FA tasks impact students' academic success?

3 Research design

This study investigated how teachers use FA tasks to assess students’ knowledge accurately and improve learning outcomes. It also examined the effectiveness of a rubric for presenting FA tasks. The purpose of such a study is to bridge gaps in knowledge by providing students with effective feedback at the right time. In the next subsection, the rubric for presenting an effective formative assessment task, participants and contexts, and data collection and analysis are considered.

3.1 Rubric for presenting an effective formative assessment task

A rubric was developed based on a survey of mathematics teachers, titled “Effective Implementation of FA in Mathematics Lessons.” (see 3.3.1) The rubric (Figure 1) allows students to indicate areas of difficulty and enables teachers to provide targeted feedback, helping students address their learning gaps. The peculiarity of the rubric here is that through the Feedback column, the student can write down the point of difficulty in completing the task, and the teacher has the opportunity to write down the student's suggestions for mistakes made and eliminate the gaps.

Formative assessment is an essential component of the learning process, designed to monitor students’ progress and provide timely feedback. While the proposed formative assessment rubric aligns with the general principles of formative assessment, it incorporates distinct features and advantages that enhance its effectiveness (Table 4)

Figure 1: Rubric for presenting a formative assessment task

Lesson №1 . Class:		Name of the student:								
Purpose of the training: 7.3.3.1 master the concepts of the main set, random sample, variational Series, variant		Feedback								
Evaluation criterion: The head knows the concepts of a set, a random sample, a variational series, can find a match;	Task. Match the definitions and statistics <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">1) General set-</td> <td>A) randomly selected part of the <u>head set</u></td> </tr> <tr> <td>2) Random selection -</td> <td>B) Location of a set of objects in ascending or descending order</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3) Version -</td> <td>B) - refers to the set of all objects and phenomena that have a general characteristic that needs to be studied.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4) Variation series -</td> <td>C) Each member of the variational series</td> </tr> </table>	1) General set-	A) randomly selected part of the <u>head set</u>	2) Random selection -	B) Location of a set of objects in ascending or descending order	3) Version -	B) - refers to the set of all objects and phenomena that have a general characteristic that needs to be studied.	4) Variation series -	C) Each member of the variational series	What was difficult for you?
	1) General set-	A) randomly selected part of the <u>head set</u>								
2) Random selection -	B) Location of a set of objects in ascending or descending order									
3) Version -	B) - refers to the set of all objects and phenomena that have a general characteristic that needs to be studied.									
4) Variation series -	C) Each member of the variational series									
Descriptor: Defines the given concepts and matches them – 1	Answer:	Teacheris suggestion:								

Table 4. Comparative Analysis

Criteria	Proposed Formative Assessment Rubric	Standard Formative Assessment Principles
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Primary Objective	Not only evaluates students' knowledge but also deepens their understanding, identifies learning gaps, and provides targeted remediation.	Monitors student progress, enhances learning, and adapts instructional strategies accordingly.
Structure	Based on explicit criteria and descriptors, providing clear guidance for both students and teachers.	Typically employs standardized tasks and observational assessments without structured rubrics.
Feedback Type	Includes personalized teacher feedback and encourages student self-assessment.	Generally, relies on oral or brief written feedback, which is often generic.
Student Engagement	Students actively identify their own challenges, propose solutions, and engage in self-reflection.	Students receive teacher feedback but are not necessarily expected to participate in the evaluation process.
Use of Assessment Results	Enables students to adjust their learning process based on feedback.	Primarily used by teachers to monitor performance and provide additional instruction if needed.
Objectivity	Uses clearly defined descriptors to ensure consistency in evaluation.	May be influenced by teacher subjectivity and observational bias.
Student Participation in Learning	Requires active involvement, self-assessment, and reflection.	Limited student engagement, as the process is primarily teacher-led.
Application of Results	Contributes to long-term learning strategies by identifying students' specific areas for improvement.	Focuses on short-term learning outcomes, which may not always lead to deeper understanding.

Advantages of the Proposed Formative Assessment Rubric Over Standard Formative Assessment Principles

Personalized Feedback: Students can pinpoint their difficulties and receive specific recommendations from the teacher.

Active Student Engagement: Unlike standard formative assessment, students participate in self-evaluation, enabling them to adjust their learning strategies.

Structured and Transparent Assessment: The rubric is based on explicit criteria and descriptors, enhancing objectivity and reliability.

Encourages Reflective Learning: Standard formative assessment often overlooks student reflection, whereas the rubric actively promotes self-analysis and critical thinking.

Limitations of the Proposed Formative Assessment Rubric Compared to Standard Formative Assessment

Time-Intensive Implementation: Teachers must provide individualized feedback for each student, which requires significant time and effort.

Dependence on Teacher Expertise: The effectiveness of the rubric depends on the teacher's ability to provide meaningful feedback and facilitate self-assessment.

Variability in Student Self-Assessment Skills: If students lack experience in self-assessment, they may struggle to evaluate their own progress accurately.

3.2 Participants and context

This study was conducted at a school in Kazakhstan, Almaty. A survey of mathematics teachers on the effective use of assessment on voluntary participation was conducted. As a result of the survey, a rubric for presenting the formative assessment task to students was developed and an experimental study was conducted. The study involved 106 students from 7

classes, in which a total of three teacher conducted classes. The control group and the research group were identified. The groups were selected according to the quality indicators of Education.

The study was carried out in algebra for 8 hours in the section "Elements of Statistics", for 2 weeks in 3 stages (summary control in the section (SCS)) (scheme 1).

Scheme 1: Stages of conducting the lesson

The steps for creating a formative assessment task for each topic are shown in scheme 2

3.3 Data collection and analysis

When collecting data, the results of questionnaires received from teachers, the results of their work on the rubric submitted for the formative assessment task are presented using a comparative indicator.

Scheme 2. Steps for compiling formative assessment tasks

3.3.1 Questionnaire from mathematics teachers

The research survey “Effective implementation of assessments by mathematics teachers in determining students 'mathematical knowledge” was conducted on a voluntary basis through the Google Form platform. 26 teachers (26 women) answered the questionnaire. The main goal here is to determine the implementation of the criterion-based assessment system and the applicability of formative assessment tasks that will eliminate gaps in students' knowledge. As a result, the question “How effectively is the criterion-based assessment system used in the assessment of students? the answer indicator of the question” is still not valid at a high level of criterion-based assessment (diagram 1). Also, in the questionnaire “Do you often use formative assessment tasks in your class? (Do you offer tasks through the handle?)” 50 percent of the teacher answered “Sometimes” (diagram 2).

Diagram 1. Application indicator of the criterion-based evaluation system

Diagram 2. Indicator of the use of formative assessment tasks by teachers in the classroom

3.3.2 Analysis of research data and results

Students completed tasks for formative assessment, which can affect academic success in the classroom, in each lesson in three stages. The presentation of tasks through descriptors at each stage allowed students with an average interest in mathematics to correctly perform calculations step by step. At the first stage, students who are not used to completing tasks using the descriptor were also often asked questions on the implementation of the tasks. At the second stage, students got used to completing formative assessment tasks, and all students mastered solving problems on the descriptor. He also had an increased interest in completing the task and was openly writing feedback. In the third stage, students noticed the difficulty in drawing the graph in time, which allowed them to carry out further corrective work. Continuous use of formative assessment tasks in three stages in one section allowed students to notice their difficulties in time, work on errors and eliminate gaps, perform calculations using a descriptor, receive feedback from the teacher, perform self-calculations, determine their level, open self-assessment and improve academic success (Figure 2).

The effectiveness of the formative assessment tasks used in each topic in three stages was determined by the results of the summary control by the section using a comparative indicator with the control group (Table 5).

Figure 2. Students' performance of tasks for formative assessment (In Kazakh)

The figure displays two pages of student workbooks. The left page contains a task on variance and standard deviation. It includes a table for calculating variance and standard deviation, and a handwritten solution. The right page contains a task on relative frequency. It includes a table for calculating relative frequency, a line graph showing the distribution, and a handwritten solution.

Table 5. Indicators of the quality of education of groups in the section "Elements of Statistics"

Group	Subject	Student N	max imu m scor e	Percentage content of aggregate assessment points				quality %	Success %
				down	environment		up		
				0-39 % (0-5)	40 -64 % (6-9)	65-84% (10-12)	85-100 % (13-15)		
Number of students									
Research group	SCS 2	25	15	0	8 (32%)	7 (28%)	10 (40%)	68	100
Control group	SCS 2	81	15	2 (2%)	26 (32%)	30 (37%)	23 (28%)	65	98

In this study, a statistical analysis was conducted to compare the academic performance of the experimental and control groups. First, the mean and standard deviation of each group were calculated. The average score of the experimental group was 11.2, while that of the control group was 10.37, with corresponding standard deviations of 2.72 and 2.75, respectively.

Levene's test was applied to check for homogeneity of variances between the two groups, yielding a p-value of 0.642, indicating that the variances were homogeneous. Subsequently, an independent t-test was conducted to compare the results of both groups statistically. The t-statistic was 1.33, with a p-value of 0.192. Since this value is greater than 0.05, the difference between the two groups is not statistically significant. Despite the lack of statistical

significance, the positive effects of the experimental teaching method were evident. Specifically, 40% of students in the experimental group scored within the 85-100% range (high scores), compared to only 28% in the control group. This suggests that the experimental approach contributed to higher academic achievement. Furthermore, no students in the experimental group scored within the 0-39% range (very low scores), whereas 2 % of students in the control group fell into this category. This indicates that the experimental teaching method helped reduce the likelihood of poor performance and motivated students to achieve higher scores.

Overall, although the mean score of the experimental group was higher, the difference was not statistically significant. However, the increase in the proportion of high-achieving students and the absence of low-scoring students highlight the potential effectiveness of the experimental teaching method. Therefore, further research is needed to assess its long-term impact.

4 Research Limitations and Potential Drawbacks

Since the study was conducted with a sample of only 106 seventh-grade students from a single school, the generalizability of the findings remains limited. Expanding the scope of the research to include students from various educational institutions and different socio-economic backgrounds would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of this assessment approach. Additionally, the study was conducted over a two-week period, which did not allow for a thorough evaluation of the rubric's long-term impact on students' academic performance. Extending the research duration to a full semester or academic year would enable a deeper analysis of its sustained effects and overall effectiveness. Another limitation is the lack of statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups ($p = 0.192$). While the rubric demonstrated a positive influence, further research is needed to strengthen its statistical validity. Incorporating additional variables, such as students' initial knowledge levels, motivation, and learning styles, would allow for a more in-depth analysis. Moreover, the consistency of teacher feedback may vary. While some educators provide detailed and constructive comments, others may limit their responses to brief or general remarks. Developing methodological guidelines and offering professional development programs for teachers could enhance the quality of the assessment process and ensure greater uniformity in feedback. Furthermore, students' attitudes toward formative assessment and their motivation levels may influence the study's outcomes. Some students may not fully engage in self-assessment or may struggle with reflection, which could affect the rubric's overall effectiveness. Overall, while the proposed rubric has demonstrated its potential to enhance student engagement and improve academic performance, further validation is needed. Expanding the research scope, extending the study duration, and providing methodological support for teachers would contribute to a more comprehensive evaluation of its long-term impact.

5 Conclusion

This study is considered a model for teachers to present a formative assessment task to students. In practice, the continuous use of the rubric for the presentation of the formative assessment task in mathematics lessons has shown that it can directly contribute to academic success. Also, the students participating in the study had the opportunity to assess themselves

fairly, identify difficulties, and eliminate gaps in time. There was a shift in the attitude of students with a "medium" interest in the subject to a higher level. However, this study also had its limitations. Due to health problems, he was unable to attend classes promptly and faced such obstacles as completing tasks at the end.

In conclusion, the use of FA tasks, because of the proposed rubric, made it possible to write down in time the most understandable and difficult part of the task for the student, as well as to establish feedback with the teacher. It has had a positive impact on academic success, albeit in a short time, by eliminating academic failures. However, in the upcoming studies, it is proposed to study formative assessment tasks using new technologies with the development of modern artificial intelligence, considering the interests and motivation of the student.

6 Resources

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